

Fermat's Principle and a Hypothetical Velocity Hypotenuse Approach

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Fermat's principle or the minimization of time in a particular scenario has been applied to the derivation of Snell's law (1) and the reflection of light from a mirror moving at a constant velocity v (2). In both these cases, conservation of the component of momentum parallel to the medium/mirror surface also applies, but in the latter case does not provide a relationship between the incident and reflected angles. Fermat's principle does not make use of momentum, only time i.e. velocities and distances. In (3) we argued that for a moving mirror one may replace Fermat's principle with the idea of a constant hypothetical velocity along the mirror surface. This velocity is hypothetical because it is a math construct which may be larger than c the speed of light. It becomes physical only when moving parallel to the medium or mirror surface in which case it moves at the speed of light or less. It acts as a hypotenuse to angled light rays in a problem (e.g. incident and refracted or incident and reflected rays).

In this note we argue that this approach also applies to Snell's law and may have a physical basis which leads to the notion of Fermat's principle which seems to be ad hoc in the sense that one does not know that time is minimized in a problem a priori. (Some arguments, however, may be made to this effect.) It seems, however, that the hypothetical velocity approach is computationally simpler at least in the two examples considered.

We also consider an interpretation of the hypothetical velocity approach using time reversal arguments.

Snell's Law

Snell's law may be derived using conservation of momentum parallel to a smooth medium (x axis) surface where $\theta(i)$ is the incident angle relative to the y axis and $\theta(r)$ the angle of refraction relative to the y axis as well. Given that the velocity in medium 1 is c/n_1 and in 2, c/n_2 and that $E=pc$, this implies that p in medium 1 is pn_1 and in medium 2, pn_2 so that E remains constant. Then:

$$pn_1 \sin(\theta(i)) = pn_2 \sin(\theta(r)) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{which is equivalent to Snell's law.}$$

Alternatively one may choose a starting point ($x=0, y=d$), medium surface at $y=0$ (along the x axis) and an endpoint ($x=L, y=-d$) and seek an x value at which an incident light ray hits the surface $y=0$. This immediately defines an angle $\theta(i)$, but also an angle $\theta(r)$. Thus one unknown x is linked to two supposed unknowns $\theta(i)$ and $\theta(r)$. Using Fermat's principle i.e. the minimization of time one may solve for x which in turn yields $\theta(i)$ and $\theta(r)$. This is equivalent to a relationship between $\theta(i)$ and $\theta(r)$ in particular:

$\sin(\theta(i)) / \sin(\theta(r)) = n_2/n_1$ with $\sin(\theta(i)) = x / \sqrt{d^2+x^2}$ and $\sin(\theta(r)) = L-x / \sqrt{d^2+(L-x)^2}$ with L , d , n_1 , and n_2 as givens. ((2))

The question is why should one minimize time a priori? A clue might be that for the above problem one may consider different x values which lead to different $\theta(i)$, $\theta(r)$ pairs, but only one is correct i.e matches a physical result. What makes this solution correct? There is nothing special about an x position, but for constant speeds one has overall time values. These differ for different scenarios. The correct result thus has a unique time value which one might suggest is an extremum or for example a minimum. One would have to verify that this is correct, but it does provide motivation for Fermat's principle.

Hypothetical Velocity Approach

In (3) we take a different approach, namely a hypothetical velocity one which is motivated in the following way. Consider a light ray moving parallel to a medium surface. In such a case, it has a velocity c/n_1 and moves along L in a time $L = c/n_1 t$. If instead one has a ray moving in n_1 and hitting an x point on the medium surface and then moving in the medium, one may consider a hypothetical velocity H (possibly larger than c) along the x axis such that the actual velocities are adjacent values to this H which acts as a hypotenuse. In particular:

$$H \cos(90-\theta(i)) = c/n_1 \quad \text{and} \quad H \cos(90-\theta(r)) = c/n_2 \quad ((3))$$

This also yields Snell's law and is based on the mathematical idea of altering a horizontal ray, but keeping the velocity H along the x axis the same. For the case of a ray moving along the x axis time is minimized so to speak because there is only one value. Light travels in a straight line which minimizes time i.e. if light deviates from moving along the x axis even slightly one might think of it making triangles with various hypotenuses which are automatically longer than the x axis projection hence leading to longer times. Thus the hypothetical H velocity is in keeping with the idea of a minimum time and minimum time is not introduced in an ad hoc manner. We suggest that the unique solution for motion parallel to a medium and representing minimum time keeps the sense of minimum time if the rays change and move at angles. It is as if a velocity on the x axis (mirror surface) is rotated and dilated into a ray at an angle. In such a case, the velocity on the x axis serves as a hypotenuse.

From a computational point of view, the H hypothetical approach seems to be more direct because one does not have to take derivatives. ((3)) may be written automatically. In (3) we apply this approach to a mirror moving at a constant v .

Mirror Moving at a Constant Velocity V

In (3) we show that the above hypothetical velocity applies to a mirror moving at a constant velocity v . In such a case we use the relative velocity of the mirror and light i.e.

$$C - v \cos(AA) \quad \text{and} \quad c + v \cos(BB) \quad ((4))$$

Then ((3)) yields: $H \cos(90-AA) = (C-v\cos(AA))$ and $H\cos(90-BB) = (c+v\cos(BB))$

Here AA and BB are the angles of the incident and reflected light with respect to the y axis with the mirror surface being along the x axis and moving along the y axis in a downward direction.

This immediately yields a relationship between AA and BB because H is eliminated.

Like in the Snell's law case, one does not have to take a derivative to obtain the relationship between AA and BB and so computation is more direct. If light were only moving along the mirror surface only c would be present. The incident light ray also moves at a speed of c so why is relative velocity used? It seems that one removes the motion of the mirror from the problem by using the relative velocities. (This suggests that this problem may be ultimately connected with special relativity.)

Like with the Snell's law case, momentum parallel to the mirror is conserved i.e.

$$P_i \sin(AA) = p_r \sin(BB) \quad ((5))$$

P_i and p_r , however, are different as are AA and BB. Thus there are 4 unknowns in ((5)).

Fermat's principle or the hypothetical velocity approach yields AA in terms of BB. If AA is known (i.e. the incident angle) as well as p_i the incident momentum, one knows p_r . An independent approach, however, (either Fermat's principle or the hypothetical velocity approach) is needed unless one wishes to solve this using special relativity. In that case, one may transform into a frame in which the mirror is not moving and use $AA = BB$ in that frame $p_i = p_r$ in that frame as well. One may then transform back to the lab.

One may note that even for a fixed mirror the H hypothetical velocity approach yields the result $AA = BB$ because:

$$H\cos(90-AA) = c \quad \text{and} \quad H\cos(90-BB) = c \quad \text{so} \quad \sin(AA)/\sin(BB) = 1 \quad \text{i.e.} \quad AA=BB$$

Moving Mirror, Hypothetical Velocity and Time Reversal

The hypothetical velocity approach may be discussed in terms of time reversal. First consider the relative velocity $c-v\cos(AA)$. The time reversed relative velocity involves interchanging AA and BB and $v \rightarrow -v$ i.e. the mirror seems to be moving up so one has $c+v\cos(BB)$. $(c-v\cos(AA))t_a$ represents the distance traveled by the incident ray on its angled path as if the mirror were not moving. $Ct_a \sin(AA) = x$ so $t_a = x/\sin(AA)c$. For the time reversed case $Ct_b \sin(BB) = L-x$. Ct_b is the distance the reflected ray travels and $v\cos(BB) t_b$ is the distance the mirror moves up projected along the reflected ray. Inserting t_b yields $(v\cos(BB) + c) (L-x)/\sin(BB)c$. Thus $v(\text{incident rel}) t_a$ is shorter than the actual distance traveled by the incident ray and $v(\text{reflected rel}) t_b$ is longer than the distance traveled by the reflected ray. If $v(\text{incident rel}) / \sin(AA) = v(\text{reflected rel}) / \sin(BB)$ as given by the hypothetical velocity then adding the two distances yields $L/c [v(\text{incident rel}) / \sin(AA)] = L/c [v(\text{reflected rel})]$. L/c is the time it takes light to travel horizontally across the length of the mirror i.e. L. In other words, the hypothetical velocity result

removes x from the sum forming a unique answer i.e. not all x and $L-x$ solutions are allowed, only the one for which the hypothetical velocity relationship between AA and BB holds. All the values i.e. v , AA, BB, t_a and t_b are measured in the lab frame. The relative velocities do not mean that one is in the moving frame. If one were in that frame, one would have $AA=BB$ i.e. the incident angle would equal the reflected.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider an H hypothetical velocity approach as the basis of Fermat's principle. We already considered this approach for a mirror moving at constant velocity v in (3), but now apply it also to Snell's law and try to argue that such an approach should yield the minimal time (as in Fermat's principle). We argue that applying minimal time a priori is an assumption whereas the hypothetical velocity approach seems to be based on changes to a velocity moving parallel to a medium or mirror surface for which minimum time is the case. Furthermore in terms of computation, the hypothetical velocity approach seems to be more direct in that it does not require taking the first derivative of a total time function.

References

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